

SAMPLE_ID	SAMPLE_ORIGIN	TYPE	SPECIES	AGE	SEX
MPC_482	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	76	F
MPC_483	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	60	F
MPC_484	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	62	M
MPC_488	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	76	M
MPC_490	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	61	F
MPC_495	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	61	M
MPC_506	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	61	M
MPC_518	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	63	M
MPC_519	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	59	F
MPC_520	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	65	M
MPC_521	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	61	F
MPC_529	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	61	F
MPC_534	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	67	F
MPC_537	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	59	M
MPC_538	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	45	F
MPC_546	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	62	F
MPC_857	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	68	M
MPC_981	CD138+BM	ULP-WGS	Homo sapiens	83	F
MPC_100	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	71	M
MPC_101	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	76	M
MPC_102	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	75	M
MPC_105	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	74	F
MPC_1107	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	64	M
MPC_111	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	65	M
MPC_112	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	39	M
MPC_113	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	58	M
MPC_116	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	43	F
MPC_117	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	69	F
MPC_118	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	53	F
MPC_12	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	63	M
MPC_121	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	69	F
MPC_122	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	68	M
MPC_123	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	69	F
MPC_124	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	74	M
MPC_125	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	60	M
MPC_127	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	71	F
MPC_129	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	62	F
MPC_134	CD138+BM	SNP	Homo sapiens	67	M

PLATFORM_COMPANY	PLATFORM_NAME	NUM_SAMPLES
Affymetrics	CytoscanHD	170
Illumina	NextSeq 500/550	83

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	LOINC	FHIR	SNOMED CT
AGE	Age	num	30525-0	birthDate	-
BM_Suv_max	Bone Marrow Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num	-	Observation.code	-
FL_sec_Impetus	Focal Lesion Impetus (Italian myeloma criteria for PET use) Score	factor	-	Observation.code	-
EM	Presence of Extramedullary lesions	factor	-	Observation.code	-
EM_DS	Extramedullary Deauville Score	factor	-	Observation.code	-
EM_SUV_max	Extramedullary Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num	-	Observation.code	-
OLD_0_1	Patients older than 60 years are scored as 1	factor	-	Observation.code	-
SEX	Sex	factor	76689-9	Observation.code	-
FISH_T_11_14	Presence of translocation t(11;14)	factor	77037-0	Observation.code	-
CREATININE	Creatinine value at diagnosis	num	2160-0	Observation.code	1032061000000108
Clearance	Clearance value at diagnosis (mL/min)	num	14682-9	Observation.code	-
HB	Hemoglobin value at diagnosis (g/dL)	num	718-7	Observation.code	38082009
PLT	Platelets value (mL)	num	26515-7	Observation.code	365632008
IG_ISOTYPE	Immunoglobulin isotype	factor	34550-4	Observation.code	-
CALCIUM	Calcium Value at diagnosis (mg/dL)	num	17861-6	Observation.code	5540006
PCR	Protein C Reactive	num	1988-5	Observation.code	55235003
RESPONSE_IND UCTION_CONTIN UATIVE	Response to continuative therapy	factor	-	Observation.code	-
CONSOLIDATIO N_RESPONSE	Response to consolidation therapy	factor	-	Observation.code	-
MAINTENANCE_ RESPONSE	Response to maintenance therapy	factor	-	Observation.code	425633006
FIRST_LINE_BES T_RESPONSE	Best response during the first line therapy. The first line includes (Induction; Transplantation or Continuative; Consolidation; Maintenance)	factor	-	Observation.code	-
PROG_I_EVENT	Progression event	factor	97509-4	Observation.code	-
PFS_I_MONTHS	Months of Progression Free Survival	num	-	Observation.code	-
OS_EVENT	Overall survival event	factor	77283-0	Observation.code	-
FL_DS_M_4	Focal Lesion Deauville Score >= 4	factor	-	Observation.valueBo olean	-
PM	Presence of Paramedullary lesions	factor	-	Observation.valueBo olean	-
CONSOLIDATIO N_YES_NO	If patients have done consolidation therapy	factor	-	Observation.valueBo olean	-
MAINTENANCE_ YES_NO	If patients have done maintenance therapy	factor	-	Observation.valueBo olean	-

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	LOINC	FHIR	SNOMED CT
PET_POS_NEG	Negative patients have Bone Marrow Deauville Score = 2 and Focal Lesion Impetus criteria =1. The remaining patients are scored as positive	factor	-	Observation.valueCo deableConcept	-
BM_DS_M_4	Bone Marrow Deauville Score >= 4	factor	-	Observation.valueCo deableConcept	-
FL_DS	Focal Lesion Deauville Score	factor	-	Observation.valueInt eger	-
PM_DS	Paramedullary Deauville Score	factor	-	Observation.valueInt eger	-
gDNA_tumor_fra ction	Genomic DNA purity baseline	num	-	Observation.valueQu antity	-
cfDNA_tumor_fr action	Circulating DNA purity baseline	num	-	Observation.valueQu antity	-
FL_SUV_max	Focal Lesion Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num	-	Observation.valueQu antity	-
PM_SUVmax	Paramedullary Standardized uptake value max (SUVmax)	num	-	Observation.valueQu antity	-
MPC	Patient identification code	character	-	Patient.identifier	-
MAINTENANCE_ THERAPHY	Maintenance therapy	factor	-	Procedure	-
CONSOLIDATIO N_THERAPY	therapy to consolidation	factor	-	Procedure.code	-
gDNA_sample_s heet_ID	DNA baseline sequencing experiment ID	character	-	DiagnosticReport	-
BM_DS	Bone Marrow Deauville Score	factor	-	Observation.code	-
Clearance_m_50	Clearance <= 50	factor	-	Observation.code	-
HB_m_10.5	Hemoglobin <= 10.5	factor	-	Observation.derivedF rom	-
PLT_m_150	Platelets <= 150 mL	factor	-	Observation.derivedF rom	365632008
PC_TOT	Total plasma cells in the marrow at diagnosis (%)	num	-	Observation.derivedF rom	-
PC_M_60	Total plasma cells >= 60%	factor	-	Observation.derivedF rom	-
R_ISS	Revised Multiple Myeloma International Staging System. 1 = Low-Risk; 2= Middle- Risk; 3=High-Risk	factor	-	Observation.code	-
LIGHT_CHAIN	Light chain class	factor	-	Observation.code	-
ECOG	Performance Status; ranges from 0 to 5, with 0 being perfect health and 5 being death	factor	-	Observation.code	-
Calcio_M_10.5	Calcium >= 10.5	factor	-	Observation.code	-
PCR_m_05	Protein C Reactive <= 0.5	factor	-	Observation.code	-
Ab_exposed	If the patient has been exposed to first- line antibody therapy (binary classification)	factor	-	Procedure	-

VARIABLE	DESCRIPTION	DATA TYPE	LOINC	FHIR	SNOMED CT
PI_exposed	If the patient has been exposed to first-line Proteasome Inhibitor therapy (binary classification)	factor	-	Procedure	-
Imid_Exposed	If the patient has been exposed to first-line Immunomodulatory agents therapy (binary classification)	factor	-	Procedure	-
PI_Imid_Exposed	If the patient was exposed to first-line combination therapy of Immunomodulatory agents and Proteasome Inhibitor (binary classification)	factor	-	Procedure	-
INDUCTION_RESPONSE	Induction therapy response. Levels: sCR= stringent CR; CR= complete response; PR= partial response; VGPR= very good partial response; SD= stable disease; PD=progression disease	factor	-	Observation.code	-
TX_I_LINE_1_0	Whether patients have had at least one first-line transplantation	factor	-	Procedure	-
NUMBERS_TX_FRONT_LINE	Numbers of transplants	factor	-	Observation.code	-
RESPONSE_TX_I	Response to first transplant	factor	-	Observation.code	-
RESPONSE_TX_II	Response to second transplant	factor	-	Observation.code	-
BEST_TX_RESPONSE	Best response to transplantation	factor	-	Observation.code	-
FRONT_LINE_INDUCTION_CONTINUE	Continuative therapy the first line. patients who are not eligible for transplantation do continuous therapy	factor	-	Procedure	-
FRONT_LINE_INDUCTION_THERAPY	First-line induction therapy	factor	-	Procedure	-
TTP_I_MONTHS	Months of time to progression	num	-	Observation.code	-
PFS_I_EVENT	Progression Free Survival Event	factor	-	Observation.code	-
LAST_FOLLOW_UP	Last patient follow-up	num	-	Observation.code	-
OS_MONTH	Months of the Overall Survivor	num	35658-4	Observation.code	-
INDUCTION_RESPONSE_M_CR	Response to induction greater than or equal to CR	factor	-	Observation.code	-
BEST_TX_RESPONSE_M_CR	Best response to transplantation greater than or equal to CR	factor	-	Observation.code	-
FIRST_LINE_BEST_RESPONSE_M_CR	Best frontline response greater than or equal to CR	factor	-	Observation.code	-

CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253
gDNA_tumor_fraction		Clearance	
Median (IQR)	0.64 (0.40, 0.84)	Median (IQR)	90 (72, 100)
Missing	170	Missing	179
cfDNA_tumor_fraction		HB	
Median (IQR)	0.06 (0.02, 0.14)	Median (IQR)	10.50 (9.00, 12.25)
Missing	170	Missing	233
BM_Suv_max		PLT	
Median (IQR)	3.35 (1.00, 4.20)	Median (IQR)	219 (177, 277)
Missing	171	Missing	7
FL_SUV_max		PC_TOT	
Median (IQR)	4.4 (0.0, 6.8)	Median (IQR)	45 (25, 80)
Missing	171	Missing	44
PM_SUVmax		CALCIUM	
Median (IQR)	0.0 (0.0, 2.0)	Median (IQR)	10.00 (9.00, 10.00)
Missing	171	Missing	232
EM_SUV_max		TTP_I_MONTHS	
Median (IQR)	0.00 (0.00, 0.00)	Median (IQR)	29 (18, 43)
Missing	171	Missing	7
AGE		PFS_I_MONTHS	
Median (IQR)	63 (57, 69)	Median (IQR)	29 (18, 43)
Missing	5	Missing	7
CREATININE		OS_MONTH	
Median (IQR)	1.00 (1.00, 1.23)	Median (IQR)	45 (29, 72)
Missing	244	Missing	7

CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253
PET_POS_NEG		PM		Clearance_m_50	
NEG	16 (19%)	0	61 (73%)	0	69 (52%)
nv	1 (1.2%)	1	21 (25%)	1	7 (5.3%)
POS	66 (80%)	nv	1 (1.2%)	nv	57 (43%)
Missing	170	Missing	170	Missing	120
BM_DS		PM_DS		HB_m_105	
2	35 (42%)	1	61 (73%)	0	150 (60%)
3	22 (27%)	3	4 (4.8%)	1	96 (39%)
4	24 (29%)	4	8 (9.6%)	nv	3 (1.2%)
5	1 (1.2%)	5	9 (11%)	Missing	4
nv (not valuated)	1 (1.2%)	nv	1 (1.2%)	PLT_m_150	
Missing	170	Missing	170	0	213 (86%)
BM_DS_M_4		EM		1	33 (13%)
0	57 (69%)	0	76 (92%)	nv	3 (1.2%)
1	25 (30%)	1	6 (7.2%)	Missing	4
nv	1 (1.2%)	nv	1 (1.2%)	PC_M_60	
Missing	170	Missing	170	0	121 (49%)
FL_sec_Impetus		EM_DS		1	86 (35%)
1	31 (37%)	1	76 (92%)	nv	38 (16%)
2	28 (34%)	4	4 (4.8%)	Missing	8
3	9 (11%)	5	2 (2.4%)	R_ISS	
4	14 (17%)	nv	1 (1.2%)	1	54 (22%)
nv	1 (1.2%)	Missing	170	2	102 (41%)
Missing	170	OLD_0_1		3	27 (11%)
FL_DS		0	152 (61%)	nv	66 (27%)
1	31 (37%)	1	96 (39%)	Missing	4
3	4 (4.8%)	Missing	5	IG_ISOTYPE	
4	28 (34%)	SEX		BJ	33 (13%)
5	19 (23%)	F	103 (41%)	IgA	43 (17%)
nv	1 (1.2%)	M	150 (59%)	IgA/BJ	2 (0.4%)
Missing	170	FISH_T_11_14		IgD	3 (1.2%)
FL_DS_M_4		0	113 (45%)	IgG	147 (59%)
0	35 (42%)	1	20 (8.0%)	IgG/BJ	2 (0.8%)
1	47 (57%)	nv	116 (47%)	nv	25 (10%)
nv	1 (1.2%)	Missing	4	Missing	4
Missing	170				

CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253
LIGHT_CHAIN		NUMBERS_TX_FRONT_LINE		FRONT_LINE_INDUCTION_CONTINUATIVE	
kappa	153(61%)	0	72 (29%)	0	167 (68%)
lambda	72(29%)	double	78 (32%)	1	68 (28%)
nv	24(14%)	nv	11 (4.5%)	nv	12 (4.9%)
Missing	4	single	86 (35%)	Missing	6
ECOG		Missing	6	FRONT_LINE_INDUCTION_THERAPY	
0	51 (44%)	RESPONSE_TX_I		DARA-VMP	1 (0.4%)
1	21 (18%)	CR	44 (19%)	IXAZOMIB-TD	1 (0.4%)
2	11 (9.4%)	nCR	2 (0.8%)	KCD	2 (0.8%)
3	6 (5.1%)	NR	1 (0.4%)	KR-R	1 (0.4%)
nv	28 (24%)	nv	89 (38%)	KRD	2 (0.8%)
Missing	136	PD	1 (0.4%)	LENA-DEX	2 (0.8%)
Calcio_M_105		PR	25 (11%)	MPD	1 (0.4%)
0	205 (81%)	RP	1 (0.4%)	MPT	3 (1.2%)
1	30 (12%)	sCR	14 (5.9%)	MPV	14 (5.7%)
nv	18 (7.1%)	VGPR	59 (25%)	nv	179 (72%)
PCR_m_05		Missing	17	RCD	1 (0.4%)
0	21 (22%)	RESPONSE_TX_II		RD	1 (0.4%)
1	36 (38%)	CR	28 (12%)	Rev-Dex	8 (3.2%)
nv	38 (40%)	CR (ALLO)	1 (0.4%)	TD	1 (0.4%)
Missing	158	nCR	1 (0.4%)	VEL-DEX	2 (0.8%)
INDUCTION_RESPONSE		nv	168 (69%)	VM-DEX	1 (0.4%)
CR	39 (16%)	PD	1 (0.4%)	VMP	24 (9.7%)
nCR	3 (1.2%)	PR	8 (3.3%)	VMP/VD	1 (0.4%)
PD	6 (2.4%)	sCR	8 (3.3%)	VRD + IXATUZIMAB	1 (0.4%)
PR	81 (33%)	VGPR	27 (11%)	VTD	1 (0.4%)
sCR	6 (2.4%)	Missing	11	Missing	6
SD	18 (7.3%)	BEST_TX_RESPONSE			
VGPR	93 (38%)	CR	50 (21%)		
Missing	7	nCR	2 (0.8%)		
TX_I_LINE_1_0		nv	92 (39%)		
0	72 (30%)	PD	1 (0.4%)		
1	164 (68%)	PR	21 (8.9%)		
nv	5 (2.1%)	sCR	14 (5.9%)		
Missing	12	VGPR	56 (24%)		
		Missing	17		

CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253	CHARACTERISTIC	N = 253
CONSOLIDATION_YES_NO		MAINTENANCE_THERAPY		FIRST_LINE_BEST_RESPONSE	
0	115 (47%)	BORTEZOMIB	17 (6.9%)	CR	80 (32%)
1	113 (46%)	BORTEZOMIB-DEX	2 (0.8%)	nCR	2 (0.8%)
nv	19 (7.7%)	CORTISONE	14 (5.7%)	nv	4 (1.6%)
Missing	6	DARA	1 (0.4%)	PD	5 (2.0%)
CONSOLIDATION_THERAPY		DARA-IXA	12 (4.9%)	PR	42 (17%)
DARA-VCD	13 (5.3%)	DARA/LENA	3 (1.2%)	sCR	24 (9.7%)
DARA-VRD	3 (1.2%)	DEX	2 (0.8%)	SCR	2 (0.8%)
IsaKRD	1 (0.4%)	IFN	1 (0.4%)	SD	9 (3.6%)
KCD	1 (0.4%)	IFN/DEX	1 (0.4%)	VGPR	79 (32%)
KRD	11 (4.5%)	INTERFERONE + DEX	1 (0.4%)	Missing	6
no consolidation	113 (46%)	ISA-KRD	1 (0.4%)	PROG_I_EVENT	
nv	21 (8.5%)	IX/PLACEBO	1 (0.4%)	0	76 (31%)
TD	2 (0.8%)	IXA	7 (2.8%)	1	170 (69%)
VCD	1 (0.4%)	IXSAZOMIB/PLACEBO	2 (0.8%)	Missing	7
VD	4 (1.6%)	KR	2 (0.8%)	PFS_I_EVENT	
VRD	8 (3.2%)	KRD	4 (1.6%)	0	71 (29%)
VTD	69 (28%)	LENA	68 (28%)	1	175 (71%)
Missing	6	no_maintenance	83 (34%)	Missing	7
CONSOLIDATION_RESPONSE		nv	19 (7.7%)	OS_EVENT	
CR	33 (13%)	TALIDOMIDE	2 (0.8%)	0	161 (65%)
nCR	4 (1.6%)	VD	2 (0.8%)	1	86 (35%)
nv	137 (56%)	VEL-DEX	1 (0.4%)	Missing	6
PD	1 (0.4%)	VELCADE	1 (0.4%)		
PR	9 (3.7%)	Missing	6		
sCR	11 (4.5%)	MAINTENANCE_RESPONSE			
SD	1 (0.4%)	CR	52 (21%)		
VGPR	50 (20%)	nv	129 (52%)		
Missing	7	PD	3 (1.2%)		
MAINTENANCE_YES_NO		PR	12 (4.9%)		
0	84 (34%)	sCR	16 (6.5%)		
1	145 (59%)	SCR	2 (0.8%)		
nv	18 (7.3%)	VGPR	33 (13%)		
Missing	6	Missing	6		